

Evaluation of Post-Operative Recovery of the Patients Underwent Minimal Invasive Procedure for Haemorrhoids (MIPH) and Open Haemorrhoidectomy

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Abstract:

Introduction: Haemorrhoids are a severe and common problem with severe bleeding along with pain, which needs extensive treatment. Two type of surgery includes for the treatment, one is Minimal invasive procedure for haemorrhoids and the other one is Open haemorrhoidectomy. There was a surgical method followed traditionally, the Milligan-Morgan technique which is characterized by severe pain and more duration for recovery. Longo introduced MIPH which shows effective pain reduction with less duration of recovery.

Aims and Objective: To evaluate the post-operative recovery of the hemorrhoids patients who received either open haemorrhoidectomy or minimal invasive procedure.

Method: The random study trial was conducted among 60 patients having two surgical procedure, one is open haemorrhoidectomy and Minimal invasive procedure for haemorrhoids. 18 to 80 years of age of patients along with baseline, testing parameter and complications before & after the surgery was considered. VAS was used for pain measurement, surgery duration and time for staying in hospital was also measured. Chi-square test, students 't' test was used for analysis of data and was evaluated using SPSS with P value <0.001.

Results: The study shows that all patients undergoing minimally invasive procedures were male (100%), while the open haemorrhoidectomy group had 80% male and 20% female patients. For grades, 95% of open haemorrhoidectomy patients had Grade III haemorrhoids compared to 85% in the minimally invasive group. Minimally invasive procedures had significantly shorter mean procedure times (24.45 vs. 39.1 minutes), lower VAS pain scores on the first (2.05 vs. 5.95) and third days (1 vs. 3.35), and shorter hospital stays (2.1 vs. 4.15 days), all with P values <0.0001.

Conclusion: The main conclusion from the findings is that minimally invasive procedures for haemorrhoids offer significant advantages over open haemorrhoidectomy.

Keywords: Hemorrhoids, Minimal Invasive, Post-Operative Recovery, VAS.

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Introduction

Haemorrhoids are a common problem affecting people globally, causing a range of symptoms from mild discomfort to severe pain and bleeding. It is characterized by vascularised, cushion forming dispo formations of thick sub mucosa with blood vessels, smooth muscles and elastic and connective tissues in the normal anal canal [1]. They are classified into internal and external types based on where they are located relative to the dentate line. While early-stage cases can often be managed with conservative treatments, more severe cases often require surgery to relieve symptoms and prevent complications [2-5].

The surgical treatment of haemorrhoids has advanced over time, with two main approaches widely used: primary surgery, such as open haemorrhoidectomy and other minimally invasive techniques, including stapled haemorrhoidopexy, or

minimal invasive procedural haemorrhoids (MIPH) [2]. A more invasive approach than its alternatives, traditional hemorrhoidectomy, involves significant tissue dissection and incisions below the dentate line, causing intense post-operative pain that can prevent normal activities for weeks [6,7]. Pain relief is provided by taking oral analgesics, maintaining regular bowel movements and using sitz baths [8]. Separation of eschatological materials occasionally leads to bleeding one week after surgery in about 1-2% patients but this condition often heals spontaneously [9]. Sub-mucosal abscesses are a rare complication accounting for less than 1% of cases while severe infections like necrotizing infections or fasciitis are even rarer. Urinary retention is commonly due to pelvic floor spasm (34%), narcotic use as well as excessive fluid administration. The solution here involves temporary insertion of Foley

catheter; usually the situation clears on its own. Fecal incontinence resulting from sphincter injury occurs in 2-10% of cases with substantial impact on daily life quality. Anal stenosis being a late complication may be due to excessive tissue removal or aggressive suturing especially when several quadrants are excised. It is difficult to manage and thus it should be avoided through having adequate mucosal bridges between excised hemorrhoids [2, 6]. Despite being an effective method, it often leads to a number of complications which includes urinary retention, bleeding and severe pain [10]. With time, the surgical techniques such as the Milligan-Morgan open hemorrhoidectomy have evolved from an original excision method with scissors towards procedures aimed at improving postoperative outcomes especially in reducing pain [11]. Presently, one of the most commonly performed surgeries to treat piles is known as the Milligan-Morgan procedure.

Milligan-Morgan technique of open hemorrhoidectomy entails making an oval incision below the dentate line to remove hemorrhoidal tissue. This method focuses on the elimination of symptoms by cutting out prolapsed tissue and lessening the pressure on other structures [12-14]. Contrastingly, Minimally Invasive Procedure for Haemorrhoids (MIPH) is a major improvement in the surgery for hemorrhoids introduced by Longo [15]. The technique is a minimally invasive one in which prolapsed hemorrhoidal tissue above the dentate line resected and once excised, it sutured back into its anatomical position without disruption of the anal mucosa with the standard stapling device [2]. MIPH is associated with less postoperative pain, shorter hospital stay and quicker recovery compared to traditional open techniques as shown in the available reports [2,16]. The MIPH procedure has sought to be less traumatic for patients and easier on surgeons by minimising tissue manipulation associated with prolapse surgery, while also potentially lowering the incidence of post-operative complications [17]. Similarly, stapled hemorrhoidopexy as a method of treating hemorrhoids was introduced in 1998 as an improvement to classical hemorrhoidectomy approaches, which is a breakthrough in the topic. Instead of taking out columns of hemorrhoidal tissue, this operation excises a cylindrical strip of distal most rectal mucosa and sub-mucosa to elevate the anal canal and fixate it the new location (thereby, anopexy) to buttress up the minimum possible mucosa redundancy [15, 18].

The MIPH process is designed to minimize patient discomfort and simplify surgery by reducing the amount of tissue handled in prolapse surgery. This approach seeks to reduce post-operative complications compared to traditional methods. Still, some patients have hemorrhoidal prolapse or anal bleeding after an operation and this happens less

frequently than with regular approaches. However, there may be a few complications that could lower patient satisfaction, such as ongoing anal pain, fecal incontinence, frequent bowel movements and the urgency for stools. Therefore, whilst it represents a step forward in terms of reduced surgical trauma from such surgeries as MIPH it is vital for realistic expectations about likely symptoms following it to be set [16,17,19-21]

Method

Research Design: This is a randomized study of evaluating the operative procedure of patient recovery from haemorrhoids, undergoing two types of surgical method, Minimal invasive procedure for haemorrhoids (MIPH) and Open haemorrhoidectomy. The study was conducted at the H.M. Patel Centre of medical care and education, Pramukhswami Medical College which is located at Karamsad in Gujarat among 60 haemorrhoids patients. The duration of the study was from 2023 July to March 2024. The study was proceeded with the written and verbal consent of the patients along with ethical community approval. Different type of baseline and testing parameters along with different arising complications before and after the surgery were considered and recorded.

Baseline parameters including age and gender, where mean of the two groups was considered. Another baseline feature was any reported bleeding or bleeding associated with prolapse. Mean value was considered for comparison of both of the groups. Testing parameters included the time of the surgery, rising complications before and after the surgery and the time for staying in the hospital. Mean value was considered for comparison of the time of surgery for both the groups. Pain after surgery was measured using visual analogue score (VAS), and VAS score was measured on the 1st and the 3rd day and chi-square test used for comparing their mean values. Early postoperative complications include two types of variables including bleeding after the surgery and urine retention. Mean value was considered for both case and for both of the groups for comparison by using chi-square test. Mean value was taken for the determining the time of staying in hospital and was compared. Recurrence is another variable for complications under delayed post-operation, where again mean values was considered. BMI evaluation of all the patients was necessary and was determined during clinical study of the patients before operation.

Inclusion Criteria

Criteria which were considered for the inclusion of the patients were-

- 18 to 80 years of age of patients were only included for the study.

- Patients with diagnosed haemorrhoids having grade 3 and grade 4 were selected for the study.
- Diagnosed haemorrhoids internally or having in both external and internal position were included for the study.

Exclusion Criteria

Criteria which were considered for the exclusion of the patients were-

- Patients with severe or mild malignancy bleeding or having incidence of bleeding from upper colonic region were excluded.
- Patients those who were below 18 years age as well as 80+ year age were not included for the study.
- Patients diagnosed with complicated haemorrhoids like thrombosed, necrotized and haemorrhoids facing infection were excluded.
- If diagnosed haemorrhoid was limited to external area only, such patients were not allowed for the study.

Statistical Analysis: Data was collected and recorded in MS Excel. The recorded data entry was done on MS excel spread sheet. Independent sample t test or students 't' test was performed for comparative study between the two groups and this was done by utilizing a software named as

statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) of version 20. Chi square test was also performed for having a comparative study of the two groups. P value was maintained at <0.001 which is statistically significant.

Result

Table 1 presents the sex and grade distribution of patients who underwent either open haemorrhoidectomy or a minimal invasive procedure for haemorrhoids. In the group that received open haemorrhoidectomy, there were 16 male patients, accounting for 80% of the group, and 4 female patients, making up the remaining 20%. Conversely, in the group that underwent the minimally invasive procedure, all 20 patients were male, representing 100% of the group, with no female patients included. Thus, each group consisted of 20 patients, ensuring a total of 100% within each category. Regarding the grade distribution of the patients, in the open haemorrhoidectomy group, 1 patient, equating to 5%, was classified with Grade II haemorrhoids, while the majority, 19 patients or 95%, had Grade III haemorrhoids. In the minimally invasive procedure group, 3 patients, or 15%, were diagnosed with Grade II haemorrhoids, and the remaining 17 patients, or 85%, had Grade III haemorrhoids. Each group, therefore, had a total of 20 patients, ensuring a complete 100% distribution.

Table 1: Sex distribution and Grade distribution of the patients in each group

	Open haemorrhoidectomy		Minimal invasive procedure for haemorrhoids	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Male	16	80	20	100
Female	4	20	0	0
Total	20	100	20	100
	Open haemorrhoidectomy		Minimal invasive procedure for haemorrhoids	
Grades	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Grade ii	1	5	3	15
Grade iii	19	95	17	85
Total	20	100	20	100

Table 2 and Figure 1 focuses on the duration of the procedure, hospital stay, and Visual Analog Scale (VAS) scores on the first- and third-days post-procedure. For the open haemorrhoidectomy group, the mean procedure time was 39.1 minutes with a standard deviation (SD) of 4.17. The minimally invasive procedure group had a significantly shorter mean procedure time of 24.45 minutes with an SD of 2.76, and this difference was statistically significant with a P value of less than 0.0001.

VAS scores, which measure pain intensity, were also assessed. On the first day post-procedure, the open haemorrhoidectomy group had a mean VAS score of 5.95 with an SD of 1.31, while the mini-

minally invasive procedure group had a significantly lower mean VAS score of 2.05 with an SD of 0.22, with a P value of less than 0.0001. By the third day, the open haemorrhoidectomy group's mean VAS score had decreased to 3.35 with an SD of 1.03, whereas the minimally invasive procedure group had a mean VAS score of 1.0 with no variation (SD of 0), again showing a statistically significant difference with a P value of less than 0.0001. The hospital stay duration also differed significantly between the two groups. Patients who underwent open haemorrhoidectomy had a mean hospital stay of 4.15 days with an SD of 0.74, compared to a mean stay of 2.1 days with an SD of 0.3 for those

who had the minimally invasive procedure. This difference was statistically significant, with a P

value of less than 0.0001.

Table 2: Duration of the procedure, hospital stay and VAS at 1st and 3rd day

S. No.	Different variables	N	Open haemorrhoidectomy		N	Minimal invasive procedure for haemorrhoids		P value
			Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1	Procedure time	20	39.1	4.17	20	24.45	2.76	<0.0001
2	VAS on 1st day	20	5.95	1.31	20	2.05	0.22	<0.0001
3	VAS on 3rd day	20	3.35	1.03	20	1	0	<0.0001
4	Hospital stay	20	4.15	0.74	20	2.1	0.3	<0.0001

Figure 1: Time of procedure, hospital stay and VAS at 1st day and 3rd day for each group

Discussion

Hemorrhoids are common anorectal disease that is caused by the inflammation of the blood vessels, causing pain and bloodshed. The treatment involves conventional hemorrhoidectomy is an open procedure where the hemorrhoid pedicle is tied through passing of a transfixing suture have been immensely successful in giving a long-standing symptomatic relief. However, a limitation of these surgeries is severe pains that are results of the operation and a major reason why patients and doctors avoid the operations. Thus, case of pain and bleeding is not considered as part of an ideal treatment of hemorrhoids.

Among the published randomized controlled trials, the safety and success of MIPH are high- lighted. Meta-analysis and systemic review of the results the randomized control trials has shown that MIPH gives have superior short term outcomes as compared to the conventional excisional techniques. [13]. The study by Shah et al., [1] also showed that MIPH had a few ben- efits over traditional hemorrhoidectomy – pain and blood loss, operative time, post-operative recovery, and hospital stay and

98.2% success rate. Hemorrhoidectomy seems to be less invasive than other transanal dearterializa- tion techniques in appearance and the operation appears to be simple and quick. However, it must be stated that during the procedure, the technical errors have an important role in the recurrence rate in comparison with the conventional hemorrhoidectomy. The major practical limitation of the procedure of MIPH is estimating of removal of the amount of prolapsed mucosa. However, the straight demeanour of common trend is that more area of Rectal mucosa must be resected when the degree of hemorrhoid prolapse is higher. However, the cost of MIPH gun was the only concern that was considerably close to acting as a major limitation.

Dealing with hemorrhoids is a common challenge that varies from mild discomfort to severe symptoms requiring surgical attention. Traditional surgeries like open hemorrhoidectomy in- volve significant tissue manipulation and cuts below the dentate line, leading to prolonged pain after surgery and potential issues like bleeding and urinary problems [6–9]. On the other hand, the Minimal Invasive Procedure for Hemorrhoids (MIPH), introduced by Longo, represents a new approach focused on

minimizing tissue trauma and speeding up recovery. By removing prolapsed hemorrhoidal tissue above the dentate line with minimal disruption to the anal mucosa, MIPH aims to reduce complications and improve patient outcomes [15–17].

Studies indicate that MIPH offers benefits such as shorter hospital stays and less post-operative pain compared to traditional open techniques [2, 16]. However, it's important to acknowledge that complications can still occur after surgery, including hemorrhoidal prolapse, anal bleeding, and in some cases, ongoing anal pain, fecal incontinence, and urgency [17, 19–21]. These findings emphasize the need to manage patient expectations about potential symptoms post-surgery.

The Milligan-Morgan open hemorrhoidectomy remains a widely practiced procedure involving the removal of hemorrhoidal tissue below the dentate line to relieve symptoms and reduce pressure on affected areas [12–14]. Despite advancements aimed at improving post-operative outcomes, including better pain management strategies [11], this approach continues to carry the risk of significant pain and complications [10].

In contrast, MIPH offers a modern approach to hemorrhoid surgery, focusing on minimal tissue trauma and faster recovery [17]. By resecting and suturing prolapsed hemorrhoids back into their normal position, the procedure aims to reduce complications like anal stenosis and fecal incontinence often associated with traditional methods [15]. However, clinical evidence shows that while MIPH reduces certain complications, it does not guarantee complete relief from symptoms, underscoring the importance of careful patient selection and follow-up [2].

In conclusion, both MIPH and traditional open hemorrhoidectomy have their advantages and challenges in treating hemorrhoids. The treatment should be directed to every patient based on their history and clinical situation. MIPH offers a less invasive option with potentially quicker recovery and fewer complications. However, it doesn't promise complete resolution of symptoms or freedom from post-operative issues such as anal pain and urgency. Moving forward, research should focus on refining surgical techniques and optimizing patient selection criteria to further enhance outcomes and patient satisfaction in hemorrhoid treatment.

Conclusion

The main conclusion from the findings is that minimally invasive procedures for haemorrhoids offer significant advantages over open haemorrhoidectomy. Specifically, the minimally invasive approach is associated with shorter procedure times, reduced hospital stays, and significantly lower pain levels as indicated by VAS scores on both the first

and third days post-procedure. Additionally, the minimally invasive procedure was exclusively performed on male patients, while the open haemorrhoidectomy group included both male and female patients. Despite the difference in patient sex distribution, the benefits of the minimally invasive procedure in terms of efficiency and patient comfort are evident. Overall, these findings suggest that minimally invasive procedures may be a preferable option for treating haemorrhoids, given their superior outcomes in terms of procedural duration, postoperative pain, and recovery time. The contributions of this study to clinical medicine are substantial. Firstly, it provides clear evidence that minimally invasive procedures for haemorrhoids are superior to traditional open haemorrhoidectomy in several key aspects. This includes shorter procedure times, which can enhance surgical efficiency and reduce operating room costs. Additionally, the significantly lower postoperative pain scores associated with the minimally invasive approach suggest improved patient comfort and potentially quicker recovery times, which can lead to earlier discharge and reduced hospital resource utilization.

Furthermore, the study's findings on the reduced duration of hospital stays for patients undergoing minimally invasive procedures highlight an important aspect of healthcare efficiency. Shorter hospital stays not only decrease the burden on hospital infrastructure but also reduce the overall healthcare costs and improve patient turnover rates.

This study also contributes to the growing body of literature supporting minimally invasive techniques, reinforcing their viability and effectiveness in clinical practice. By demonstrating the tangible benefits of these procedures, this research can guide clinicians in their decision-making process, potentially leading to broader adoption of minimally invasive techniques in the treatment of haemorrhoids.

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